

Table 1. Primary antibody table

Peptide/protein target	Antigen sequence	Name of antibody	Manufacturer, catalog No.	Species raised in; monoclonal or polyclonal	Dilution used
phosphatase and tensin homologue deleted on chromosome ten (PTEN)	Carboxy-terminal sequence of human PTEN.	PTEN (26H9)	Cell Signaling, 9556S	Mouse; monoclonal	1:100
green fluorescent protein (GFP)	Purified recombinant GFP emulsified in Freund's adjuvant	Anti-GFP (green fluorescent protein)	AVES, GFP-1010	Chicken; polyclonal	1: 1000
kisspeptin	N terminus of the full-length mouse KISS1 protein	Anti-kisspeptin	Abcam, ab19028	Rabbit; polyclonal	2 ug/mL
kisspeptin	Ten amino acid C-terminal of murine kisspeptin (residues 43–52)	Anti-kisspeptin Batch #566	Alain Caraty, Institute National de la Recherche Agronomique, Paris, France	Rabbit; polyclonal	1:10,000
β -actin	Amino-terminus of human β -actin	β -actin	Cell Signaling; 13E5	Rabbit; monoclonal	1:1000
P70 S6 kinase	Residues surrounding (Ser235 and Ser236)	Phospho-S6 Ribosomal protein	Cell signaling, 2211S	Rabbit; polyclonal	1: 200

A.

B.

Supp. Fig. 1. (A) Representative photomicrographs of adult WT and Kiss-PTEN KO testicular tissue (cross-section) showing normal seminiferous tubules and spermatogonic cells (Sg, spermatogonia; Sz, spermatozoa). (B) Representative photomicrographs of adult WT and Kiss-PTEN KO ovaries (CL, corpus luteum). Scale bars: (A) = 50 μ m; (B) = 200 μ m.